

Characterization of Pure Nanostructure ZnO and its Application as Gas Sensor

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ABSTRACT

The ZnO nanostructures have been synthesized and studied as the sensing element for the detection of H₂S gas. The ZnO nanostructures were synthesized by Sol-gel method followed by sonication. By using screen printing method, thick films of synthesized ZnO nanostructure were deposited on glass substrate. Gas sensing properties of ZnO nanostructure thick films were studied for low concentration H₂S gas at different temperature. ZnO nanostructure synthesized by this method can be used as a promising material for semiconductor gas sensor to detect gas like H₂S at room temperature with high sensitivity and selectivity.

Keywords: Nanostructure ZnO, Characterization; UV, FTIR, XRD, TEM, SEM and H₂S Sensor.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sensor science and engineering is relevant to virtually all aspects of life including safety, security, surveillance, monitoring, and awareness in general. Owing to recent consciousness in environmental pollution, there is a growing need for reliable and inexpensive gas sensors and monitoring systems for industrial process and production areas. The modern industrial monitoring is based on the capability of measuring and controlling physical and chemical parameters such as temperature, pressure and chemical composition. Hence, the development of specific and efficient sensors is a necessity. Recently, sensors has

been using for a variety of purposes such as detection of smoke, radiation, hazardous gases. This demand has been created by an increasing concern for pollution monitoring and improved safety in various environments, both industrial and domestic. In addition, these sensors could have an important role in the intelligent automatic control of a large number of processes, ranging from microwave cooking to the efficient combustion of motor engines¹. Sensors are also central to medicines being used for diagnostics, monitoring, critical care, and public health.

Gas sensors play an important role in our everyday life in which we gather information, process it and perform some task. Yet, the successful application of a sensor is determined by its performance, cost and reliability. Recent technological developments both in the knowledge of the sensing principles and enabling technologies have led to the design of superior sensors with linear outputs. These sensors, which analyze or identify atmospheric gases, are useful in many fields of human activity including detection of toxic and explosive gases inside mines, gas leak inside residences and the control of atmospheric pollution. Aside from other applications, gas sensors are heavily used in areas like environmental monitoring, biotechnology, chemical analysis, and on-line detection of products. Thus, sensors open a wide range of applications from home to factory floor. They were first developed in Japan for devices such as gas leak alarms and measuring instruments. In addition, gas sensors make a major impact on many other different applications in areas like automotive industries, oil industries etc.

Nanostructured materials such as ZnO, SnO₂, and WO₃ have shown good electrical properties²⁻¹³. Among these nanostructure-semiconducting materials, ZnO has been studied extensively for electrical application and gas sensing. Due to its versatility and multifunctionality creates attention in the research field related to its electrical applications and gas sensing. A wide number of synthesis techniques also been developed by which ZnO can be grown in different nanoscale forms. Efforts were made to synthesize ZnO nanostructure with innovative morphology by Sol-gel method. The synthesized ZnO shows good electrical conductivity. In the present work, the efforts are made to study Characterization and gas sensing of low cost (ZnO).

H₂S is a toxic gas produced from the coal, oil and natural gas industries. In order to enhance the sensitivity and selectivity of H₂S, many attempts were made to synthesized nanostructure ZnO with different morphologies¹⁴⁻¹⁸.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Synthesis of ZnO Nanostructure

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used as purchased without further purification. In present work, Zinc nitrate hexahydrate was dissolved in distilled water such that to make 0.15 M solution. Subsequently, 0.5 M NaOH aqueous solutions were introduced into the above aqueous solution drop by drop with constant stirring. The resultant white solution was subsequently kept at 75 °C For 12 hrs and then cooled room temperature

naturally and sonicated (Ultrasonic wave treatment) for 30 min. The resulting white precipitates were collected by centrifugation, washed with distilled water and ethanol several times and then dried at 80°C in vacuum oven for 2hr. Obtain ZnO nanostructure product were used for further study.

2.2. Preparation of Thick Films

Thick films of synthesized nanostructure ZnO were prepared by using screen printing technique. In present process, thixotropic paste was formulated by mixing the synthesized ZnO powder with ethyl cellulose (a temporary binder) in a mixture of organic solvents such as butylcellulose, butyl carbitol acetate and turpineol. The ratio of ZnO to ethyl cellulose was kept at 95:05. The ratio of inorganic to organic part was kept as 75:25 in formulating the pastes. The thixotropic pastes were screen printed on a glass substrate in desired patterns. The films pre-prepared were fired at 500°C for 12 hr. Prepared thick films were called as pure ZnO thick films.

3. MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION

3.1. Thickness Measurement

Thickness of all ZnO thick films were measured by using technique “Marutek film Thickness Measurement System” with the help of provided equipment. The thicknesses of all films were observed in the range from 35 μm. Thick films of approximately uniform thicknesses were used for further characterization.

3.2 UV-visible absorption spectrum

UV-visible absorption spectroscopy is widely used tool for checking the optical properties of nanosized particles. Figure 3.2 shows the UV-visible absorption spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles calcined at temperature 800°C for 6 Hrs. From the spectrum four peaks are observed at 362nm, 318nm, 344nm and 296nm, out of this at 318 nm wavelength has been found maximum absorption, if we calculate band gap for this wavelength it is 3.30eV, which is very close to the band gap of ZnO 1s–1s electron transition (3.37eV)¹⁹.

3.3 FTIR analysis

FTIR analysis spectrum shown in figure 3.6, indicating significant absorption peaks at wave numbers 4350, 4200, 3900, 3850, 1700, 1550 and 600, 510 cm⁻¹. The absorption band at 600 and 510 cm⁻¹ is obtained due to existence of Zn-O bond stretching vibration²⁰. The peaks at 1700 and 1550 cm⁻¹ shows H-O-H bending vibration due to the adsorption of moisture, when FTIR sample disks were prepared in an open air atmosphere. The remaining peaks between 4350 to 3850 cm⁻¹ are corresponding to O-H stretching vibrations²¹.

Figure 3.2 UV-visible absorption spectrum of Pure ZnO

Figure 3.3 FTIR absorption/transmission spectrum of Pure ZnO

3.4X-Ray Diffraction Studies

The crystallographic structure of the synthesized ZnO nanostructure was characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (Philips X-ray diffractometer) with Cu- α source and 2θ range of $10^\circ - 70^\circ$. Fig 1 shows the XRD pattern of the ZnO nanostructure. The recorded XRD pattern confirmed that synthesized ZnO are highly crystalline in nature. The corresponding X-ray diffraction peak for (100), (002), (101), (102) (110), (103) and (112) planes confirm the formation of hexagonal wurtzite structure of ZnO (JCPDS card no.-01-080-0075). The domain size of the crystal can be estimated from the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the peaks by means of the Scherrer formula,

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \sin\theta}$$

where λ is the wavelength of incident beam (1.5406 \AA), β is the FWHM of the peak in radians, θ is the diffraction angle and K is Scherrer constant. The average particle size was calculated from (101) peak ZnO is found to be 78 nm.

Using X'pert High Score Plus software it is confirm that synthesized zinc oxide powder contains Zn and O elements only, not any impurity and another element.

Figure 3.4 X- Ray diffraction Pattern of Pure Zinc Oxide (ZnO)

3.5 Transmission electron microscope

Figure 3.5 shows transmission electron microscope image of ZnO nanostructure synthesized by Sol-gel method. It is clearly seen from the TEM image that the ZnO powders consist of large number of nanosphere which were cumulated to form superior size crystal.

Fig 3.5 (a)

Fig 3.5 (b)

3.6 Scanning Electron Microscopic Study

Figure 3.6 shows typical SEM images of the pure ZnO thick film prepared by screen printing technique. The ZnO synthesized by the Sol-gel method consist of randomly distributed nanosphere as shown in Figure 3.6(a),(b) Due to such a deposition of nanosphere, surface to volume ratio of the ZnO may be increase.

Fig 3.6 (a)

Fig 3.6 (b)

4. ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES

4.1. I–V characteristics

Figure 4.1 depicts the I–V characteristics of the pure ZnO films at room temperature. The symmetrical nature of I–V characteristics shows that silver contacts on the film are ohmic in nature²².

Figure 4.1 I-V Characteristics of Pure ZnO Thick Films

Figure 4.2 A.C. Conductivity of Pure ZnO Thick Film

4.2 For Measurement of A.C. Conductivity

A.C. electrical conductivity of the thick films was measured by using Agilent 4284A LRC meter. Variation of electrical conductivity with the frequency was observed in the frequency range 100- 1MHz at room temperature.

The A.C. conductivity of pure ZnO thick films measured in the frequency range of 100Hz to 1MHz at room temperature. The experimental data reveal that ac conductivity increases with frequency (Figure 4.2) Variation of A.C. conductivity with frequency can be explained with the help of barrier hopping mode²³.

4.3 Gas Sensing Properties

The gas response of the sensor was defined as the ratio of the change in conductance of a sample upon exposure to the target gas to the original conductance in air. Figure 4.3 shows the gas responses of ZnO thick films to H₂S at operating temperature. This high response of ZnO thick film to H₂S may be due to the interaction of ZnO with H₂S, forming ZnS²⁴. ZnS exhibits higher electronic conductivity as compared to pure ZnO.

Figure 4.3 sensitivity of gas from mixture of gases

Figure 4.3 also indicates the pure ZnO have maximum gas response to low concentration H₂S. The higher response ZnO nanostructure upon exposure to H₂S may be attributed to the decrease in concentration of oxygen adsorbents (O²⁻_{ad}) and a resulting increase in concentration of electron.

The gas response was mainly dependent upon two factors. The first was the amount of active sites for oxygen and the reducing gases on the surface of the sensor materials. It is seen from TEM images Figure 3.6 (a),(b). The surfaces pure ZnO contain more active sites. This could explain why the response of pure ZnO thick films was higher than other thick films.

5. CONCLUSION

In summary, sensors were fabricated with ZnO nanostructures, which were synthesized by a sol-gel method followed by sonication, and their gas sensing properties were measured. The results demonstrated that pure ZnO is very sensitive to low concentration H₂S. Such nanomaterials with innovative structure can be used for gas sensors to monitor hazardous gas like H₂S.

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